

DEFINITION OF TECHNOLOGY AND TECHNOLOGY INTEGRATION

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Abstract. *Use of Technology in English Language Class Technology is an effective tool for learners. Learners must use technology as a significant part of their learning process. Teachers should model the use of technology to support the curriculum so that learners can increase the true use of technology in learning their language skills. Teachers should find methods of applying technology as a useful learning instrument for their learners although they have not learnt technology and are not able to use it like a computer expert. The application of technology has considerably changed English teaching methods. It provides so many alternatives as making teaching interesting and more productive in terms of advancement.*

Key words: *technology, a computer expert, activities, curriculum.*

ОПРЕДЕЛЕНИЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ И ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОЙ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ

Аннотация. *Использование технологий на уроках английского языка. Технология – эффективный инструмент для учащихся. Учащиеся должны использовать технологии как значительную часть своего учебного процесса. Учителя должны моделировать использование технологий для поддержки учебной программы, чтобы учащиеся могли более эффективно использовать технологии в освоении своих языковых навыков. Учителя должны найти методы применения технологий в качестве полезного инструмента обучения для своих учеников, хотя они не изучали технологии и не могут использовать их как компьютерные эксперты. Применение технологий значительно изменило методы преподавания английского языка. Он предоставляет так много альтернатив, как сделать обучение интересным и более продуктивным с точки зрения прогресса.*

Ключевые слова: *технологии, компьютерный специалист, деятельность, учебная программа.*

Technology has been defined by different researchers. According to İŞMAN (2012), it is the practical use of knowledge particularly in a specific area and is a way of doing a task especially using technical processes, methods, or knowledge. The usage of technology includes not only machines (computer hardware) and instruments, but also involves structured relations with other

humans, machines, and the environment (İŞMAN, 2012). According to Hennessy, Ruthven, and Brindley (2005) and Pourhosein Gilakjani (2017), technology integration is defined in terms of how teachers use technology to perform familiar activities more effectively and how this usage can re-shape these activities.

Dockstader (2008) defined technology integration as the use of technology to improve the educational environment. It supports the classroom teaching through creating opportunities for learners to complete assignments on the computer rather than the normal pencil and paper. Use of Technology in English Language Class Technology is an effective tool for learners. Learners must use technology as a significant part of their learning process. Teachers should model the use of technology to support the curriculum so that learners can increase the true use of technology in learning their language skills (Costley, 2014; Murphy, DePasquale, & McNamara, 2003). Learners' cooperation can be increased through technology. Cooperation is one of the important tools for learning. Learners cooperatively work together to create tasks and learn from each other through reading their peers' work (Keser, Huseyin, & Ozdamli, 2011).

Bennett, Culp, Honey, Tally, and Spielvogel (2000) asserted that the use of computer technology lead to the improvement of teachers' teaching and learners' learning in the classes. The use of computer technology helps teachers meet their learners' educational needs. According to Bransford, Brown, and Cocking (2000), the application of computer technology enables teachers and learners to make local and global societies that connect them with the people and expand opportunities for their learning. They continued that the positive effect of computer technology does not come automatically; it depends on how teachers use it in their language classrooms. According to Susikaran (2013), basic changes have come in classes beside the teaching methods because chalk and talk teaching method is not sufficient to effectively teach English.

Raihan and Lock (2012) state that with a well-planned classroom setting, learners learn how to learn efficiently. Technology-enhanced teaching environment is more effective than lecture-based class. Teachers should find methods of applying technology as a useful learning instrument for their learners although they have not learnt technology and are not able to use it like a computer expert. The application of technology has considerably changed English teaching methods. It provides so many alternatives as making teaching interesting and more productive in terms of advancement (Patel, 2013). In traditional classrooms, teachers stand in front of learners and give lecture, explanation, and instruction through using blackboard or whiteboard. These methods must be changed concerning the development of technology. The usage of multimedia texts in classroom assists learners in become familiar with vocabulary and language structures.

The application of multimedia also makes use of print texts, film, and internet to enhance learners' linguistic knowledge. The use of print, film, and internet gives learners the chance to collect information and offers them different materials for the analysis and interpretation of both language and contexts (Arifah, 2014). Dawson, Cavanaugh, and Ritzhaupt (2008) and Pourhosein Gilakjani (2014) maintained that using technology can create a learning atmosphere centered around the learner rather than the teacher that in turn creates positive changes. They emphasized that by using computer technology, language class becomes an active place full of meaningful tasks where the learners are responsible for their learning. Drayton, Falk, Stroud, Hobbs, and Hammerman (2010) argued that using computer technology indicates a true learning experience that enhances learners' responsibilities.

Technology encourages learners to learn individually and to acquire responsible behaviors. The independent use of technologies gives learners self-direction. According to Arifah (2014), the use of internet increases learners' motivation. The use of film in teaching helps learners to realize the topic with enthusiasm and develop their knowledge. Learners can learn meaningfully when technology is used in the process of learning through using computer and internet. When learners learn with technology, it assists them in developing their higher order thinking skills. It can be concluded that the true combination of multimedia and teaching methodology is very important to attract learners' attention towards English language learning.

The literature review indicated that technology resources cannot guarantee teachers' teaching and learners' learning. Teachers should be convinced of the usefulness and advantages of technology in improving learners' learning. This means that teachers need support and training for integrating technology into language teaching. The review revealed that when technology is used appropriately, it can bring about a lot of advantages to teachers and learners. It is a resource that can be used by learners because it helps them solve their learning problems and find methods to use what they have learnt in ways that are effective and meaningful. In addition, the review literature indicated that the use of technologies plays a key role in language learning based on their own pace, helps in self-understanding, does not stop interaction with the teacher, and creates high motivation in learners for the effective learning of language skills.

Furthermore, the paper represented that learners should use technology to enhance their language skills because it has as a crucial role in developing learners' creativity and provides them with interesting, enjoyable, and exciting alternatives to study the language. To sum up, the findings of this literature review showed that technology provides interaction between teachers and learners, provides comprehensible input and output, helps learners to develop thinking skills,

makes learning and teaching becomes more student -centered, promotes learners' autonomy and helps them feel more confident, and increases learners' motivation to effectively learn a foreign language.

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